

REMODEL WORK PACKAGES

The simplicity of REMODEL overall work packages structure, where each work package concentrates in a set of complementary tasks aligned to the work package objectives, with some overlapping between interrelated work packages and tasks, will make project management easier, by providing clear responsibilities and assessment of progress and thereby will help reduce the risks involved in completing the project successfully.

The work plan of REMODEL consists of 20 tasks in 5 work packages. The project duration is 36 months (January 1st, 2023 – December 31st, 2025).

WPs No.	Work Packages and Tasks Title	2023												2024												2025											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
WP1	Project Management	[Active]																																			
T1.1	Administrative and financial coordination	[Active]																																			
T1.2	Technical coordination, quality control & risk management	[Active]																																			
T1.3	Ethics and data management	[Active]																																			
WP2	Bursa Uludag University Research Capacity Building	[Active]																																			
T2.1	Capacitation on marketing and consumer behaviour methodologies and supporting tools	[Active]																																			
T2.2	Capacitation on innovation & leadership strategies, methodologies and tools	[Active]																																			
T2.3	Bursa Uludag University BMI Laboratory set-up	[Active]																																			
T2.4	Research management, proposal writing methodologies and tools	[Active]																																			
WP3	Twinning and Networking	[Active]																																			
T3.1	Definition of the common strategic research agenda	[Active]																																			
T3.2	REMODEL summer schools	[Active]																																			
T3.3	REMODEL staff exchanges	[Active]																																			
T3.4	Long-term networking and R&I cooperation strategy	[Active]																																			
WP4	Research on Innovative Business Models Leveraging the BMI Lab	[Active]																																			
T4.1	Analysis of hospitality sector in Turkey	[Active]																																			
T4.2	First round of innovative business models for SMEs in the hospitality sector	[Active]																																			
T4.3	BMI Lab methodology optimisation	[Active]																																			
T4.4	Second round of innovative business models for SMEs in the hospitality sector	[Active]																																			
T4.5	Novel BMI impact assessment, feedback collection and improved methodologies	[Active]																																			
WP5	Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Outreach	[Active]																																			
T5.1	Dissemination and communication	[Active]																																			
T5.2	Exploitation	[Active]																																			
T5.3	Liaison and clustering activities	[Active]																																			
T5.4	R&I policy recommendations	[Active]																																			

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